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МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ УПРАВЛІННЯ РОЗВИТКОМ ДЕРЖАВНО-ПРИВАТНОГО ПАРТНЕРСТВА В УМОВАХ ПОВОЄННОГО ВІДНОВЛЕННЯ ЕКОНОМІКИ УКРАЇНИ

У статті досліджено і обґрунтовано управління розвитком державно-приватного партнерства в умовах повоєнного відновлення економіки України. Доведено, що одним із можливих ефективних рішень щодо подолання кризових явищ та сучасних викликів для підприємств сьогодні є узгодження та кооперація діяльності бізнесу через їх залучення до інтеграційних процесів із державою для формування інноваційного вектору повоєнної розбудови і розвитку. Обґрунтовано, що системи управління розвитком державно-приватного партнерства є драйверами становлення та розвитку нових галузей і видів діяльності об'єднаних суб'єктів малого та середнього підприємництва. Доведено, що активний розвиток державно-приватного партнерства здійснюється приватним бізнесом за участі різних партнерів-учасників. Вітчизняні реалії управління розвитком державно-приватного партнерства характеризуються слабким інституціональним середовищем та відсутністю / браком підтримки з боку держави. Встановлено, що в умовах воєнної економіки все більшого поширення набувають інтегровані форми підприємництва у вигляді проектів державно-приватного партнерства, створення та подальший розвиток яких засновано на мережесих засадах горизонтальної інтеграції та інтерактивної взаємодії господарюючих суб'єктів бізнесу, що становитиме одну з ключових компонент післявоєнного відновлення економіки.

Ключові слова: бізнес, інтеграція, інтегровані форми підприємництва, інноваційний розвиток, інфраструктура, договори концесії, державно-приватне партнерство, економічні процеси, екосистема, управління розвитком державно-приватного партнерства.

Табл. 2. Літ. 10.

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MODELING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN THE CONDITIONS OF POST-WAR ECONOMIC RECOVERY OF UKRAINE

The article studies and substantiates the management of the development of public-private partnership in the conditions of post-war economic recovery of Ukraine. It is proved that one of the possible effective solutions to overcome crisis phenomena and modern challenges for enterprises today is the coordination and cooperation of business activities through their involvement in integration processes with the state to form an innovative vector of post-war development and development. It is substantiated that the management systems of the development of public-private partnership are drivers of the formation and development of new industries and types of activities of united entities of small and medium-sized businesses. It is proved that the active development of public-private partnership is carried out by private business with the participation of various partner participants. Domestic realities of managing the development of public-private partnership are characterized by a weak institutional environment and the absence / lack of support from the state. It has been established that in the conditions of the war economy, integrated forms of entrepreneurship in the form of public-private partnership projects are becoming increasingly widespread,

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the creation and further development of which is based on network principles of horizontal integration and interactive interaction of business entities, which will constitute one of the key components of the post-war economic recovery.

Keywords: business, integration, integrated forms of entrepreneurship, innovative development, infrastructure, concession agreements, public-private partnership, economic processes, ecosystem, management of the development of public-private partnership.

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Problem statement. Public-private partnership is an effective mechanism for activating innovative and investment processes during the wartime economy.

For Ukraine, which is facing the unprecedented challenge of post-war recovery, public-private partnership ceases to be one of the possible options and turns into an alternative process of reconstruction and restoration. The scale of destruction of critical infrastructure, industrial facilities and housing requires colossal investments that significantly exceed the fiscal capabilities of the state. Innovation-oriented management of public-private partnership projects will allow Ukraine not only to restore its economic potential, but also to make a qualitative leap, modernize the national economy in accordance with EU standards and lay the foundation for long-term sustainable development.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The interaction of business and government is the key to the effectiveness of the post-war reconstruction of the national economy. The most promising form of such interaction, according to scientists and practitioners I. Grishchenko, L. Hanushchak-Efimenko, I. Gnatenko, is public-private partnership, which provides the possibility of implementing large-scale and high-cost projects, establishing long-term partnerships between business and government, sharing risks between project participants, implementing modern technical solutions and innovations, ensuring effective management of newly created facilities, involving the private sector in the implementation of socially significant projects and development policies [3].

The relevance of the study is based on the results of analyzing domestic and foreign experience in managing the development of public-private partnerships, their institutional support, as well as practical significance in the conditions of war and post-war economic recovery.

The purpose of the article is to substantiate the theoretical foundations and develop scientific and practical proposals for the formation of a model for managing the development of public-private partnership in the conditions of post-war economic recovery in Ukraine.

Presentation of the main results. In recent years, against the backdrop of aggravation of crisis phenomena in global markets and in the national economy in particular, deepened at first by the challenges and consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic, and after the invasion of the Russian Federation into the territory of Ukraine, further exacerbated by full-scale military operations and the devastating destruction of an unprecedented number of infrastructure facilities, domestic business has found itself in an extremely difficult situation. On the one hand, the rapid growth of IT technologies and the penetration of the achievements and developments of the Fourth Industrial Revolution into all spheres of life force entrepreneurs to take meas-

ures to increase their competitiveness through the use of the latest innovative tools in their activities, without which it is practically impossible to obtain real competitive advantages in the domestic and international markets. On the other hand, the traumatic events caused by the war have had an impact on the emergence of social tension within the country, provoked excessive turbulence in absolutely all economic processes, the inability to predict the destruction of certain value-added chains, led to bankruptcy and cessation of the activities of a significant number of business entities due to the lack of proper conditions for doing business. In addition, constant threats to the life, health and safety of the population, loss of human capital due to mass internal and external migration and a number of other problems caused by military actions have "clamped" the business sector and forced it to switch to a survival strategy for the most part.

Under such circumstances, perhaps the only promising options for business are to actively search for ways to maintain old and develop new market niches, deepen the diversification of its own production and provision of services, and join forces of separate business units with state institutions to address issues of maximizing profits and reducing costs.

The Law "On Public-Private Partnership" [4] was adopted in 2010, and in 2019 – the new Law "On Concession" [5], unfortunately, this form of interaction between business and government has not been significantly widespread over the past 13 years.

According to the results of the analysis, as of 01.01.2023, 193 public-private partnership agreements (hereinafter referred to as PPPs) were concluded, of which nine concession agreements, five joint activity agreements and four other agreements are being implemented, and the rest (162 agreements) are not being implemented: 116 are not being implemented, 46 are terminated, 13 are suspended due to the armed aggression of the Russian Federation [8].

The state of PPP implementation in Ukraine has improved somewhat. Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented as of 01.01.2025, amounted to 22 units, including 22 contracts in the Kyiv region. Comparative statistical analysis and its graphical presentation are shown in Table. 1 [8].

Table 1. Status of PPP implementation in Ukraine. Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented, 2021, 2023, 2025, based on [8]

Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented as of 01.01.	2021	2023	2025
Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented	24	18	22

If we track the number of contracts concluded under PPP terms and implemented as of January 1, 2025 by region, the largest number is in Kyiv region - 4, including 2 in the healthcare sector (Table 2).

The issues of cooperation between business and government are characterized by the following influencing factors: a high level of overregulation of economic activity (over 50 thousand regulatory and legal acts regulating entrepreneurial activity); instability of government policy; unsatisfactory quality of the business climate (weak judicial system, high level of shadow economy and corruption); ineffective regulation of

the sphere of natural monopolies; insufficient level of protection of intellectual property; ineffective interaction with tax authorities; lack of prerequisites for formalizing relations between government and business; imperfection of the institution of legal and moral and ethical norms of business participation in political decision-making processes that affect economic development. On the other hand, 80.1% of businesses do not interact with local authorities or communities, and 94.1% of businesses do not know whether they are included in support programs [8].

Table 2. Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are being implemented as of 01.01.2025 by region, based on [8]

Contracts concluded under PPP terms, which are implemented as of 01.01.2025	Tourism, leisure, recreation, culture and sports	Water collection, purification and distribution	Production, transportation and supply of heat and distribution and supply of natural gas	Others	Healthcare	Waste management, except collection and transportation
Volyn	1					
Dnipropetrovsk		2				
Zhytomyr			1			
Transcarpathian		1	2			
Zaporizhzhia		1		1		
Ivano-Frankivsk	1					
Kyiv	1	1			2	
Kirovohrad	1					
Lviv		1				
Mykolaiv		2				
Odesa						1
Poltava						1
Khmelnyskyi				1		
Chernihiv			1			

A study of the implementation status of public-private partnership projects in Ukraine, conducted based on data from the Department of Public Procurement and Competition Policy of the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine as of early 2025, reveals a critical gap between the number of formally concluded agreements and their actual implementation. Of the cumulative portfolio of 200 agreements concluded under PPP terms, only 11% (22 agreements) are in the active implementation phase. The structure of active projects is diversified: 9 – in the form of concession agreements, 6 – in the form of joint activity agreements and 7 agreements concluded in other forms stipulated by law. At the same time, the vast majority (83.5% or 167 agreements) are inactive. This array includes 114 agreements that are not being implemented by the parties, which indicates a high level of defaults or systemic problems in the implementation of obligations, and 53 contracts whose life cycle has ended due to termination or expiration. A separate factor reflecting modern challenges is the suspension of the implementation of 11 projects due to force majeure circumstances caused by the full-scale armed aggression of the Russian Federation. Thus, empirical data confirm the low effectiveness of the PPP mechanism in Ukraine in practice and the high level of attrition (disposal) of projects [88].

The figures characterizing the state of implementation of PPP agreements in Ukraine, unfortunately, illustrate the main problem: despite hundreds of formally valid agreements, only two large, systemic PPP projects structured according to international standards have been implemented in Ukraine.

Conclusions. According to the results of modeling the management of the development of public-private partnership, it is worth highlighting priority vectors for Ukraine:

Formation of a "knowledge ecosystem" (scientific research and analytics should be focused on specific, pilot projects, and not on abstract models, in order to avoid discrepancies between theory and practice) and the formation of a powerful technology transfer center, centralized or local in the form of clustering. This is the basis for the success of attracting investment funds and strengthening trust in PPPs.

Prioritization by economic sectors has been determined for the intensive launch of the market and the effectiveness of PPP projects.

The course of European integration and transparency of PPP projects. Ukraine should use its EU candidate status as a political tool to advance difficult but necessary reforms in the areas of PPP, public procurement, and anti-corruption policy.

Realistic expectations in an effective PPP policy. Ukraine should prepare for a situation where the reconstruction of schools, hospitals, and housing will largely require other financing mechanisms (grants, direct budget investments, loans from international financial institutions), and PPPs will be used only in specific cases.

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